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07068297660
support@gamjiinstitute.org**

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AN APPRAISAL OF THE TREATMENT AND CARE OF GUNSHOT VICTIMS ACT, 2017

By

Agbo Friday Ojonugwa*, Mary Arthur-Jolasinmi**

**LLB, BL, LLM, MIMHL, MMLP, Ph.D Faculty of Law Veritas University Bwari, Abuja FCT.
kingschild4you@gmail.com, kingschild4u@yahoo.com Phone Number: +2347033963763.*

***B.A (Hons), LLB, BL, LL.M: Ph.D, Faculty of Law Philomath University, Kuje, Abuja FCT
Email: Maryfaithj@philomath.edu.ng, faithjolas@yahoo.com: Tel: +2348068938316*

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ABSTRACT

Gunshot wound and the problems associated with it has always been a global health phenomenon. Due to the sensitive nature of gunshot injuries in any clime, the treatment of victims is a pertinent and constant controversy among stakeholders particularly victims and their family, Governments, Medical Practitioners, Police, “Good Samaritans”, Legal Practitioners and relevant scholars. Prior to December 2017, victims of gunshot wounds could not be treated in Nigerian Hospitals without a police report which has led to the death of hundreds of thousands of victims in Nigeria. In 2017, the Nigerian President, Muhammudu Buhari signed the Compulsory Treatment and Care for Victims of Gunshot Act (2017) into law and being a legislation enacted by the National Assembly, is binding on all States in the Federation. The Doctrinal methodology was employed in this work. This Paper recommends that the government should promote legal awareness of the Act in collaboration with civil societies, the Nigerian Medical Association, and the Nigerian police via sensitization programs, workshops, seminars etc. People knowing their rights and duties will encourage them to demand justice and ensure enforcement at all levels explores the provisions of this new Act and the responses of both the Public and Private hospitals in treating victims of gunshot wounds without a police report.

Keywords: Appraisal, Treatment, Care, Gunshot, Victims.

1. INTRODUCTION

Significantly, gunshot wounds and the problems associated with them have always been a global health challenge and are still so. Most developed countries like the United States of America, the United Kingdom etc., have put in a lot of human and capital resources to ensure that this menace can be eradicated in their nations or at least curbed to its barest minimum.

Unfortunately, most developing countries suffer the problems associated with Gunshot wounds more than the developed countries. On its own part, Nigeria has made efforts to tackle this bull by its horn by promulgating the Compulsory Treatment and Care of Victims of Gunshot Act, 2017.

However, it is disparaging to see that despite the Compulsory Treatment and Care for Victims of Gunshots Act, the old and wrong practice of demanding police report to treat patients and refusing to treat them in the absence of one is still very much prevalent and practiced in Nigeria today. However, before we discuss the legal issues surrounding the barely sensed execution of the Compulsory Treatment and Care for Victims of Gunshot Act 2017, we shall first explore the Act itself, with its underlined provisions.

The Act makes provision for various rights and obligations as well as penalties. These rights, obligations, and penalties shall be considered below in relation to the provisions of the Act as stipulated in the sixteen sections therein.

2. RIGHTS OF A VICTIM OF A GUNSHOT

It is the right of a gunshot victim to be received and accepted for immediate treatment. Section 1 of the Act provides for this thus:

As from the commencement of this Act, every hospital in Nigeria whether private shall accept or receive, for immediate and adequate treatment with or without police clearance, any person with a gunshot wound¹.

1. Right to be assisted by every person and security agent to the nearest hospital for immediate treatment. Section 2 (1) of the act states:

Every person, including security agents, shall render every possible assistance to any person with gunshot wounds and ensure that the person is taken to the nearest hospital for immediate treatment.

2. Likewise, it is the right of a gunshot victim to be treated without an initial monetary deposit. Section 2 of the Act ensures this right is provided thus:

(2) Accordingly-

2. a person with a gunshot wound shall be received for immediate and adequate treatment by any hospital in Nigeria with or without initial deposit.

3. Fourthly a gunshot victim has a right to be treated humanely. Section 2 (b) provides:

S.2 (b) a person with a gunshot wound shall not be subjected to inhuman and degrading treatment or torture by any person or authority, including the police or other security agents.

1. A gunshot victim has a right not to be invited for interrogations unless a bill of good health has been passed by the Chief Medical Director. Section 4 of the Act provides:

The police shall not invite any person with gunshot wounds from the hospital for the purposes of investigation unless the Chief Medical Director of the hospital certifies him fit and no longer in dire need of Medicare.

1. RIGHTS /DUTY OF PERSONS (A VOLUNTEER OR HELPER OF GUNSHOT)

Section 2(1) of the Act (supra) enjoins every person to be a “Good Samaritan” every time they come across a gunshot victim by assisting them to the nearest hospital. Similarly, though not categorically stated, Section 2 (b) of the Act (supra) further protects the Good Samaritan from being harassed by the hospital in demanding they pay deposits before treatments can begin. Even though some Good Samaritans do not mind, most persons refuse to help victims of emergencies in general because of this practice. The Act also accords volunteers or helpers of gunshot victims the right to be treated with respect and not to be subjected to unnecessary and embarrassing interrogations from security agents. Section 8 of the Act provides thus:

Every volunteer or helper of a victim of gunshots shall be treated with respect and shall not be subjected to unnecessary and embarrassing interrogation in their genuine attempt to save life.

It should be noted that section 8 of the Act does not specifically provide for the protection of doctors and any other health workers who help a victim of a gunshot outside the health care facility and/or their hours of duty. It can, however, be rightly deduced that section 8 protects such health care workers as they can be deemed to be acting as good Samaritans at that moment.

4. OBLIGATIONS OF THE HOSPITAL.

1. First and foremost, every hospital in Nigeria, whether public or private, has the obligation not to reject any gunshot victim brought to it for medical attention. Section 1 of the Act (supra) covers and tackles the very bane of contention regarding gunshot victims in Nigeria, demanding police clearance before treatment can commence. Section 2(2) (a) (supra) also reiterates the provision of section 1 on receipt of gunshot victims by hospitals for immediate and adequate treatment with or without police clearance.

2. Hospitals also should report to the nearest police station the presence of a victim or victims of a gunshot in its facility. Section 3(1) of the Act provides:

a hospital that receives or accepts any person with a gunshot wound shall report the fact to the nearest police station within two hours of commencement of treatment.

3. Hospitals have a duty upon demand to make statements as they may be compelled to incriminate the victim as provided for under S.6 of the Act.

It should be noted that S.3(1) of the Act (supra) buys more time for the hospital to notify the police of the victim of a gunshot in its facility as against the notion and practice where hospitals are expected to immediately notify the police of the presence of a victim of a gunshot wound before treatment can commence. This provision also estops the Nigerian police from harassing and arresting health care personnel for commencing treatments without police clearance.

The question now is, is 2 hours sufficient time to report the presence of a gunshot victim on its premises? The chaos of trying to save and severity of time when saving the life of a victim of a gunshot is enough pressure on the hospital. They do not need the additional pressure of trying to contact the police within 2 hours of admission and attempt to treat such a victim. The writer's opinion is that 2 hours is insufficient to notify the police. It does not relieve them of the pressure to notify the police immediately where a gunshot victim is brought to the hospital for treatment. The protection provided for doctors should they decide to render treatment to gunshot victims without a police report is limited by reason of the 2 hours stipulated by the Act.

4. Hospitals also have a duty to notify family members or relations of the presence of a gunshot victim in its care when they become aware of his identity. Section 10 of the Act states that:

A hospital that receives any person with gunshot wounds shall notify the family members or relations of the victim as far as they may ascertain within 24 hours of becoming aware of the victim's identity.

Hospitals have an obligation to keep adequate records of treatment. Section 12 of the Act provides that:

A hospital or facility that takes or receives for treatment any person with gunshot wounds shall keep adequate record of the treatment.

Although not stated in the Act, such records will go a long way in enhancing and facilitating medico legal investigations carried out by the police and other forensic experts regarding the investigation of the gunshot.

5. Hospitals also have an obligation to ensure that the victim is fit and no longer in need of dire Medicare before the chief Medical Director certifies him fit to be invited by the police for investigation. S.4 of the Act (supra).

Section 8 (1) of the Robbery and Firearm (Special Provisions) Act 2004 (as amended 2021) provides that a police officer or a member of the armed forces may arrest without warrant any person reasonably suspected of having committed or of being about to commit an offence under this Act and the police officer or member of the armed forces may use such force, including the use of firearms, as may be reasonably necessary to effect the arrest of that person or to prevent his escape. This provision has been abused over the years, especially regarding detention, arrest, and interrogation of victims of gunshot wounds suspected to be armed robbers. S.4 cited above does not just admonish the police from forcefully taking gunshot injury victims in for interrogation when they are not properly fit. It also admonishes hospitals not to release victims to the police until they are certain they are medically necessary fit.

2. RIGHTS AND OBLIGATION OF RELATIONS

The relations of the victim of a gunshot wound owe a duty to:

1. Hospitals owe relations the specific duty to notify them of the presence of victims under their care as stipulated under section 10 of the Act (supra).
2. Relations have a duty to Make statements as stipulated under Section 6 of the act states as follows:

.... A person who receives the report under section 3(2) of this Act shall furnish or the hospital on demand, with background information on the victims as he may be compelled to incriminate the victim.

3. OBLIGATION OF THE POLICE/SECURITY AGENTS

The responsibilities of the police as stipulated under the Act include:

1. All security agents are not left out in ensuring that the high morbidity and mortality rate associated with gunshot wounds is tackled in Nigeria, hence their duty to render assistance to any person with gunshot wounds and ensure they are taken to the nearest hospital. This is provided for under section 2 (1) of the Act (supra).

2. The police are also saddled with the responsibility or duty of treating victims of gunshot wound humanely and without degrading treatments or torture as provided for under S. 2 (2)(b) of the Act (supra).

S.2 (2)(b) was specifically added into the Act to curb instances where the police have been reported to request and sometimes go to the hospital and arrest and detain victims of gunshots to the police stations for their statements under the shield of investigation.² This provision is also in line with the right to the dignity of the human person guaranteed in the 1999 constitution. A person who is arrested must not be subjected to any form of torture, cruel, inhumane or degrading treatment.³ This provision is also included in the Administration of Criminal Justice Act.⁴ Hence a violation of this provision by the police and other law enforcement agencies is not just a violation of the provision of the 2017 Act but also a violation of the provision of the 1999 Constitution (as amended), the Police Act 2020, and the ACJL 2015.

3. The Act provides for the duty of the police to commence an investigation to ascertain the circumstance that led to the shooting once a gunshot case is reported to them. This is provided for under section 3 (2) of the Act, which states that:

upon receipt of the report under subsection (1) of this section, the police shall immediately commence investigation with a view to determining the circumstances under which the person was shot.

One of the major duties of the police with regards to gunshot victims is an investigation of the crime hence the insertion of this section in the Act. However, the challenges confronting

2 See Research' <<https://legalsnaija.com>> accessed 21st July, 2021 and Unini (n27).

3 Section 36 Police Force (Establishment) Act, 2020

4 Section 8(1) of The Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2015.

investigations and investigators in the Nigerian Criminal Justice System are myriad. On duties of Police and Power to arrest without warrant, the Court of Appeal in *Statmak v C.O.P*⁵ held that:

Section 4 of the Police Act, Cap. 359, Laws of the Federation 1990 states the duties of the police to include, amongst others, the prevention and detection of crime, the apprehension of offenders, the preservation of law and order, the protection of life and property a due enforcement of all laws and regulations with which they are charged. Once criminal allegations are made against a citizen, the police has a constitutional and a statutory duty to investigate the allegations. In carrying out these tasks, the police is empowered under the provisions of section 24 of the Police Act to arrest without warrant any person whom any other person charges with having committed a felony or misdemeanor. Provided, as states in section 27 of the Police Act, that a person so arrested without warrant shall be taken before a magistrate within a reasonable time or granted bail with or without sureties at the police station. By these provisions of the police Act read along with the proviso of section 35 (1), 41 (2) (a) and 45 of the 1999 constitution, it is clear that where it is shown that the police acted reasonably within its powers under the Police Act, in the investigation of a criminal complaint and with reasonable grounds to believe that a person had committed a criminal offence or is likely to commit one, the necessary curtailment of the fundamental rights of such a person cannot amount to a breach of that persons fundamental rights.

The court of appeal decision in the above-cited case clearly shows that the police can investigate and even arrest the person so far as it is carried out within the ambits of the provisions of the law and hence the arrest of the person. The provision of section 3(2) of the Compulsory Care and treatment of Gunshot Victims Act 2017 further confirms this power of the police. However, this power to investigate is being guided by certain provisions of the 2017 Act already discussed and further to curtail abuse of this right regarding gunshot victims.

⁵ [2020] 9 NWLR (pt1728) 176.

A study conducted between 2006 and 2009 and focused on criminal investigations as a component of the criminal administration of justice in Nigeria indicated some challenges of criminal investigations in Nigeria. A few of which include⁶:

- i.** The common practice of unforthcoming informants who refrain from coming forward in case they might get into some sort of trouble
 - ii.** Lack of Funds to carry out investigations
 - iii.** Corruption in the Nigerian Police Force.
 - iv.** Lack of training of investigating Police officers who mostly dont even know what to do nor the international best practice for investigations.
 - v.** Missing case files: The embarrassing phenomenon which springs from absence or the ineffective running of the central investigation file registries at police stations and at all levels of the police structure.
 - vi.** Delayed duplication of case files: Part of the duty of an investigating police officer is to have case files duplicated and transmitted to the office of the Director of Public Prosecutions from legal advice, especially where capital offences, serious offences, and technical offences are involved. As straightforward as this process is, it has constituted a significant bottleneck in the Nigerian criminal justice system as criminal matters have been known to be bogged down at this stage of the criminal administration of justice for up to two years or more.
 - vii.** Lack of Forensic Laboratories and insufficient Number of trained experts: applying scientific knowledge and methods to the investigations of crimes and the solution of knotty criminal riddles is routine in the developed world, but this is not the case in Nigeria, where forensic investigations are still novel.
 - viii.** Poor Public recordkeeping: with the grave deficiency in public records and archives in Nigeria, the criminal investigator is placed at a significant disadvantage, and the best possible criminal investigation results are unattainable.
1. The police owe the victim the duty not to invite him/her for investigation unless a fitness certificate is issued. This is provided for under S. 4 of the 2017 Act (supra).
 2. To furnish the hospital with background information of the victim?

6 Oluwafemi Alexander Ladipo, Effective Investigations, A pivot to Efficient Criminal Justice Administration: Challenges in Nigeria *African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies* [2011] (5) (1-2) <<https://www.umes.edu>> accessed 21st July, 2021.

7. PENALTIES UNDER THE ACT

1. Failure of hospitals to make a report to the police attracts a penalty. Section 5 of the Act provides that:

A hospital that fails to make a report as required under section 3 of this Act commits an offence and is liable on conviction to a fine of ₦100, 000.00 and every doctor directly concerned with the treatment is equally liable on conviction for a term of six months or a fine of ₦100, 000.00 or imprisonment or both.

2. Withholding of information stipulated under S.6 of the Act also attracts a penalty. S.7 of the Act provides for the penalty as follows:

A person who fails, neglects or refuses to give the report required under section 6 of this Act commits an offence and is liable on conviction, or a fine of ₦50, 000.00 or imprisonment for a term of six months or both.

3. Persons guilty of an offence under this Act shall incur the penalty stipulated in S.9 of this Act as follows:

A person who commits an offence under this Act which leads to or causes substantial physical, mental, emotional, and psychological damage to the victim commits an offence and is liable on conviction to imprisonment for a term of not more than 15 years and not less than five years without an option of fine.

4. The offence of standing by shall attract the penalty specified in S.11 of the Act as follows:

Any person or authority, including any police officer, other security agents or hospital who stands by and fails to perform his duty under this Act which results in the unnecessary death of any person with gunshot wounds, commits an offence and is liable on conviction to a fine of ₦500, 000.00 or imprisonment for a term of five years or both.

5. Any corporate body that commits an offence shall attract the penalty provided for under S.13 of the Act thus:

A corporate body that commits an offence under this Act, the head of the corporate body shall be prosecuted in accordance with the provisions of sections 11 and 14 of this Act.

6. The courts also have the power by reason of the provision of this Act also to impose a penalty of restitution on any person or corporate body in violation of the provisions of the Act. This is provided for under S.14 of the Act thus:

14. (1) in addition to any other penalty under this Act, the High Court shall order a person or corporate body convicted of an offence to make restitution to the victim by directing that person or corporate body to pay to the victim an amount equivalent to the loss sustained by the victim.

(2) An order of restitution may be enforced by the victim or by the prosecution on behalf of the victim in the same manner as a judgment in a civil action.

The last two sections of the Act, Section 15 and 16, provide for the interpretation and citation of the Act, respectively.

8. CONCLUSION

Going by the provisions of the Compulsory Treatment and Care for Victims of Gunshots Act, lack of treatment and care, death, demand for police reports before treatment can commence, demand for deposits etc. should be a nightmare long overhauled and forgotten in Nigeria.

With the unsettling incidences of gun violence on the rise daily in Nigerians due to insurgencies, kidnappings, thuggery, and cultism, more innocent people are victims of gunshots, the relevance of the Act cannot be disparaged. It will be a horrific experience for anyone to be shot and denied immediate medical care and treatment just because the emergency is a gunshot wound. The government must do whatever it takes to ensure that this law is implemented to save lives and eliminate or at least bring to the barest minimum gunshot injuries and gun crimes at all cost.

1. RECOMMENDATIONS

- i.** The government needs to create a dedicated and accessible national fund to help offset medical bills of victims of gunshot who are treated but later elope without paying their bills.
- ii.** The researchers recommend the creation of a good Samaritan authority as enshrined in section 3 of the Indian Good Samaritan (Protection from Civil and Criminal Liabilities) And Miscellaneous Provisions Bill, 2014 and to carry out the functions stipulated in

section 4 of the Act therein to ensure enforcement and implementation of the 2017 act, handling complaints, ensure payment of claims, sensitisation of the public to be good samaritans and on the provisions of the Act.

- iii.** The Medical and Dental Practitioners Council of Nigeria should aid the government in enforcing this Act by reiterating compliance with provisions of the 2017 Act in their rules of conduct. The Medical and Dental Practitioners Disciplinary Committee should further intensify sanctions for violation of the 2017 Act.
- iv.** The Act should be included in all academic institutions, the Police College and Medical School Curriculum. This will go a long way in aiding awareness of the Act and its provisions.
- v.** The proliferation of arms must be checked and fiercely fought. More stringent gun control measures must be put in place like registration of firearms and holders of unregistered firearms be heavily punished.
- vi.** Security agents at airports, seaports, borders of Nigeria must be sensitized on the dangers of being lax and allowing the proliferation of arms into the country. Integrity on their part must be emphasized. Likewise, stern penalty measures must be enforced against such security agents found wanting.
- vii.** The researchers also advocate for not just sensitization of the provisions of the Compulsory Treatment and Care for Victims of Gunshots Act 2017 but also the upholding of the punishment for default of the provisions of the Act by all parties concerned. The punishment should also be made more stringent to intensify adherence.